

AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS 3D PRINTING AMONG MECHANICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS IN A STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This study significantly determines the awareness and attitude of fourth year Mechanical Engineering students about the functions and the benefits in utilizing 3D Printers. In order to conduct a study, participants answered a survey questionnaire, using 5-point Likert scale to measure the magnitude of their agreement and opinion. There is a total of 32 fourth year Mechanical Engineering students in a chosen public higher education institution who participated in the survey. The content in the survey are related to the different types of 3D Printers available in the market but limited to material extrusion types, their awareness on the features and cost of 3D Printers, and their behavior towards it. The data were encoded and analyzed using SPSS through T-test, ANOVA and Pearson's r method. It has been discovered that the students have fair comprehension or exhibit neutrality regarding the types of 3D Printing, and their awareness about the existing of 3D Printers. On the other hand, participants expressed their positive attitude on eagerness to learn and know more about 3D Printing technology. Moreover, participants believed that the benefits and contribution of 3D Printing in integrating to the subject curriculum in educational institution will enhance their skills and expertise in hands-on learning experiences, foster creativity and innovations, and prepare them as a future professional in helping diversify the community to meet the technology trends.

Keywords: *3D Printers Awareness; Emerging Technology; 3D Printer on SUC*

INTRODUCTION

Technology makes life easier and safer. It's true that technology is altering our personal lives and the whole world in an almost infinite number of ways. Regardless, it is typical for people to criticize these accomplishments. (Jones, 2022)

Modern technology in this modern era gives a big impact and changes in the society and every community. The evolution of these inventions makes the living easier, better, and faster from a conventional appliances to an automated and controlled electronically. Businessman and innovator benefited the importance of modern technology especially in digital fabrications because the digital fabrication as a whole, makes the processing more easily and faster in their specific products and projects. When it comes to education and in academe, digital fabrication is new in mind especially to those who are not aware about the new technology arrived.

Introduction to digital fabrication for higher education institution is a mix of excitement to those who are willing to explore the new technology and confusion to those who have no knowledge with the technology. Digital fabrication is a series of manufacturing and design process where the data process from one software drives another software or equipment to form a geometrical shapes or figures. One of the most popular digital fabrication existing nowadays is 3D printing. The 3D printing is an additive manufacturing just like a printer that prints in 2D and makes a series of layer until the model from the layout will complete that can be seen and touched.

3D printing has recently become a critical tool in the geoscience research, education, and technical communication due to the expansion of the market for 3D printers and materials. 3D printing changes the perception of how we interact with our data and how we explain our science to non-experts, researchers, educators, and stakeholders. (Ishutov et al., 2021).

Digital fabrication is an emerging new technology for the developing countries. In higher education institution, awareness of 3D printing technology was not yet implemented due to newly established laboratory under research and this advanced technology is not included in the course curriculum of students. The current conventional teaching of faculty is more on theories, illustration and explanation which the students cannot appreciate because they could not see the actual appearance. If the 3D printing is introduced to class lectures, the students could understand and gain more knowledge regarding its potential uses and benefits.

In the Philippines, the inclusion of 3D Printing in the curriculum is still an unusual practice in schools. Unlike in western countries where 3D Printing had been made a standard part of the school curriculum, from grade school to the tertiary level. (CIIT Philippines School - Multimedia Arts, Web Design, 3D Animation, Mobile Game Development, 2019)

3D printing technology in higher educational institution has limited approach to digital fabrications due to the inadequate understanding or introduction of new technology that only exists on other countries. During the assessment with the teaching personnel of public higher education institution using Key Informant Interview (KII), teachers expressed their sentiments about the low literacy on the importance of digital fabrications among the students like 3D Printing technology. Teachers wished to include the kinds of digital fabrications that existed in the market like 3D Printers to the curriculum to enhance the student's skills and knowledge in line with their chosen profession as future engineers.

To fill the gaps between the industry and academe, government agency like the Department of Trade and Industry initiated and spearheaded the establishment of Fabrication Laboratory (FabLab) in State University wherein the agency provided machines and equipment including the 3D printing, through the collaboration of Department of Science and Technology to train, give advice and develop new ideas to the instructors. 3D printing offers a world of possibilities, but it has its limitations. Stanford researchers are stretching the boundaries of current printing models and finding innovative ways to solve pressing dilemmas of design, engineering, and medicine. (Banks, 2023)

In general, there was an educational effect through 3DP lessons that the students were able to more deeply understand the current market demands and use of 3DP in various industries including fashion and gain their interest in 3D modeling and 3DP in the fashion field. (Kwon et al, 2017). By establishing the Fabrication Laboratory in State University, faculty, researchers and students can broaden their knowledge in the field of science and technology areas that complement their course curriculum, and bridge the academe-industry integration for further research and development of the graduate professionals.

Research Objectives

This study generally aims to determine the awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing among Mechanical Engineering students in a State University.

Specifically, this study has the following objectives:

1. Describe the student's profile in terms of sex, age, and geographical location;
2. Describe the level of awareness and attitude of Mechanical Engineering students in a state university in 3D Printing technology in terms of FDM, Bio-printing, and Construction 3D as classified according to sex, age, and geographical location;
3. Determine if there is significant difference in the level of awareness and attitude of Mechanical Engineering students in a state university in the types of 3D Printing technology in terms of FDM, Bio-printing, and Construction 3D as classified according to sex, age, and geographical location; and
4. Determine if there is significant relationships in the awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing among Mechanical Engineering students in a state university.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of this study utilized Quantitative approach and Descriptive Inferential type. The researcher observed, collected and analyzed the numerical data based on the statistical relationship of student's awareness and the student profile. This study provided a detailed explanation or description of characteristics and behaviors of particular population. The data was taken on a small sample of respondents to draw inferences with regards to the larger population.

Connectivism learning theory state that knowledge has many authors, knowledge has many facets, it looks different to each person, and it changes moment to moment. A piece of knowledge isn't a description of something, it is a way of relating to something. (Downes, 2021).

This research utilizes connectivism and transformative learning theory based on the study of Western Governors University (2020 and 2021) wherein the learners gained new knowledge and information that essentially changed their view in the world, and in the influence of new technology that existed. In this theory, the students are identifying the gaps in their knowledge about the emergence of digital fabrications in the universities and colleges.

The Figure 1 below illustrates the relationship of antecedent variable, independent variable, and dependent variable about 3D printing awareness and attitude of fourth year Mechanical Engineering students of a state university. The student's profile in terms of sex, age, and geographical location is identified as antecedent variables. The types of 3D printing printers limited to materials extrusion like Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), 3D Bio-printing, and Construction 3D Printing refers to independent variable. The dependent variable in this study are their awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing. An assumption has been stated that the Types of 3D Printing technology has significant relationship to the awareness and attitude among the Mechanical Engineering students in state university. Additionally, an assumption proposed that the student's profile in terms of sex, age, and geographical location are significantly related to their awareness and attitude. The hypothesized interaction of the variable is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1

Awareness and Attitude Towards 3D Printing Among Mechanical Engineering students in a state university.

2.2 Research Locale

The researcher used a purposive sampling technique to ensure the alignment of the research goals and to obtain more meaningful results. Using this sampling technique, the researcher intentionally chose individuals who could provide valuable insights relevant to the study. The respondents of this study were fourth-year students taking up Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering from Iloilo Science and Technology University - Main Campus. Data was collected during the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024. The Mechanical Engineering course was chosen due to the relatable application of 3D printing technology to their profession in designing and prototyping.

2.3 Research Participants

The researcher used a purposive sampling technique to ensure the alignment of the research goals and more meaningful results. Using this sampling technique, the researcher intentionally chose individuals that can provide valuable insight with regard to the research study. The respondents of this study were the fourth (4th) year students taking up Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering from Iloilo Science and Technology University - Main Campus. The data was taken during the second semester

of academic year 2023-2024. The researcher chose on Mechanical Engineering course due to a relatable application of 3D printing technology to their chosen profession in designing and prototyping.

2.4 Research Instrument

The instrument used in gathering data on 3D printing awareness was survey disseminated to the respondents through a hard copy questionnaire. In this instrument, the respondents answered the survey form/questionnaire by checking the appropriate box in relation to their awareness and attitudes towards 3D printing. The questionnaire consisted of four sections.

The first part of questionnaire collected personal details of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and geographical location.

Likert scale questions allow respondents to share their level of agreement with a statement using a numerical scale. A Likert rating scale is useful for measuring opinions, attitudes, and knowledge. (Houston, 2024)

The second part of the main questionnaire was on the types of 3D Printing technology which is limited only to material extrusion type specifically its sub-types like Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), 3D Bio-printing, and Construction 3D Printing. Using 5-point Likert scale, each item in the questionnaire determined the respondent's degree of agreement and disagreement with the statement based on the following criteria:

- 5 = Strongly agree
- 4 = Agree
- 3 = Fair
- 2 = Disagree
- 1 = Strongly disagree

The third part of the main questionnaire was on the awareness of the respondents towards 3D Printing. Each item in the questionnaire determined the respondent's degree of agreement and disagreement with the statement based on the following criteria:

- 5 = Strongly agree
- 4 = Agree
- 3 = Fair
- 2 = Disagree
- 1 = Strongly disagree

The fourth part of the main questionnaire was on the attitude of respondents towards 3D Printing. Each item in the questionnaire determined the respondent's degree of agreement and disagreement with the statement based on the following criteria:

- 5 = Strongly agree

- 4 = Agree
- 3 = Fair
- 2 = Disagree
- 1 = Strongly disagree

Content Validity of the Questionnaire

Content validity is the degree to which a test or assessment instrument evaluates all aspects of the topic, construct, or behavior that it is designed to measure. (Frost, 2024)

The questionnaire was reviewed and validated by consultants who have expertise in the field regarding for some suggestions for improvements and changes. The consultants are manager of fabrication laboratory, college instructor in software applications, and research adviser.

Reliability of the Questionnaire

PSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) is a software package used for statistical analysis in the social sciences, including fields such as monitoring and evaluation. It was originally developed in the late 1960s by IBM and has since become one of the most widely used statistical software packages in the world. (EvalCommunity, 2023)

The reliability of the software application used was analyzed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). In this tool, data collected are encoded in the system to generate statistical data like frequency counts, percentage analysis, means and standard deviations. This tool also tabulated results using T-test, ANOVA, and Pearson's r methods.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection provides the basis for reliability estimations. Thus, a good data collection procedure is crucial to ensure that the reliability estimate is trustworthy. A prediction is never better than the data on which it is based. (Wohlin, 2003)

The procedure of this study on gathering data are based on stated step by step process as follows:

- i. The first step was to identify the total population of the fourth year students taking Mechanical Engineering. Due to a small number of entire group and researcher's own judgment to select individuals to meet the specific criteria relevant to the research question, the researcher used Purposive sampling and chose the entire fourth year Mechanical Engineering students of a chosen public higher education institution. In using purposive sampling, the research goals of the research aligned which leads to a more focused results.

ii. After establishing of number of target respondents, the next step was to develop survey form for respondents chosen. The contents of survey form included the respondent's profile in terms of sex, age, and geographical location. The survey included the respondent's understanding of the 3D printing, the several types of material extrusion, and the level of awareness of participants in 3D printing technology.

iii. Before the survey, the questionnaire was validated through pretesting. Through this procedure, the developed survey was check and verified by the experts or the people who understand the specific study so that the questionnaire would be understandable and interpretable by the intended respondents.

iv. When the survey form was completed, the questionnaire was endorsed to the College Dean including the request for conducting the survey to participants which are the students of the university. With this, the researcher was granted permission on taking data to the students and the College Dean was aware of the conduct of the study.

v. The researcher selected respondents in a random procedure. The gathering of data was taken as an entire group regardless of the respondent's section he or she belong.

vi. Before taking the survey, the researcher obtained consent from the students based on the guidelines of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This law enacted by the Philippine government to provide and protect the personal and sensitive data from the respondents. By disclosure consent of participant to researcher, the researcher treated the data with utmost confidentiality.

vii. After the consent, the questionnaire was given to the respondents directly and they answered the respective questions stated in the form. The respondent's answer is in the form of checklist and based on their awareness about 3D printing technology.

viii. After answering, the forms were collected for data analysis procedure and discuss the results.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are implemented in research as it needs to adhere to the code of conduct when it comes to collecting data from participants. The goal of this research is to give information and understanding on the importance of 3D printing for the advancement of technology in the university specifically the fourth year Mechanical Engineering students in integrating the 3D printer in academe. Participants were informed of the risks and they gave consent to answer the survey. Their data were kept with utmost confidentiality. After the survey, the researcher collected the answered questionnaire.

RESULTS

Questionnaire Type used to Determine the Awareness and Attitude of students

A 5-point Likert scale is used in answering the questionnaire with the following equivalent: 5 = Strongly agree means the respondent has highest level of agreement or conviction in a statement, 4 = Agree means the respondent has positive response to the statement with some extent but not strong as “strongly agree”, 3 = Fair means the respondent has a neutrality or indicating neither agree or disagree in a statement, 2 = Disagree means respondent has negative response to the statement with some extent but not strong as “strongly disagree”, and 1 = Strongly disagree means has highest level of disagreement in a statement.

Interpretation of Data Scaling

For the mean scale, the following are the equivalent point: 4.20-5.00 = Strongly agree means the respondent has highest level of agreement or conviction in a statement, 3.40-4.19 = Agree means the respondent has positive response to the statement with some extent but not strong as “strongly agree”, 2.60-3.39 = Fair means the respondent has a neutrality or indicating neither agree or disagree in a statement, 1.80-2.59 = Disagree means respondent has negative response to the statement with some extent but not strong as “strongly disagree”, and 1.0-1.79 = Strongly disagree means has highest level of disagreement in a statement.

For T-Test (used in 2-groups), ANOVA (used in 3 or more groups), and Correlation, the following are the interpreted values: If p-value(significance) > level of significance (alpha), the null hypothesis is accepted. If p-value(significance) < level of significance (alpha), the null hypothesis is rejected, and accept alternative hypothesis. In this study, the value of alpha is set at 0.05.

Student's Profile

The total number of fourth year mechanical engineering students in the Iloilo Science and Technology is 32 including both male and female. Table 1 below shows the complete headcount and percentage of the respondents based on the respondent's filling of survey forms:

Table 1a

Describe the student's profile in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	20	62.5	62.5	62.5
Female	12	37.5	37.5	100.0
Total	32	100.0	100.0	

The result in Table 1a shows that the majority of the fourth year Mechanical Engineering students of Iloilo Science and Technology University are male composed of 62.5 percent compared to female composed only of 37.5 percent in terms of sex.

Table 1b

Describe the student's profile in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
21	2	6.3	6.3	6.3
22	26	81.3	81.3	87.5
23	3	9.4	9.4	96.9
24	1	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Table 1b above shows that the common age of fourth year mechanical engineering students is 22 years old composed of 81.3 percent. The rest are one or two year above and below the common age.

Table 1c

Describe the student's profile in terms of geographical location

Geographical Location	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Urban	13	40.6	40.6	40.6
Rural	19	59.4	59.4	100.0
Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Table 1c above shows that the graphical location of fourth year Mechanical Engineering students are majority living in a rural area with composition of 59.4 percent compared to urban area with 40.6 percent.

Types of 3D Printing Technology among Mechanical Engineering students

This study described the various 3D Printing Technology perceived by the mechanical engineering students according to sex, age, and geographical location. In introducing the several types of 3D Printing Technology, the researcher limited the scope to Material Extrusion types of 3D Printers like Fused Deposition Modeling, Bio-printing, and Construction.

In the survey form, respondents were given questions related to identifying the brief definition of types of 3D Printing Technology limited to Fused Deposition Modeling, Bio-printing and Construction 3D.

Table 2a

Types of 3D Printing Technology perceived by students in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Male	2.7500	20	1.07265
Female	2.7500	12	0.76045
Total	2.7500	32	0.95415

Table 2a shows that both male and female respondents are in a 2.75 mean scale (falls in 2.60-3.39 - Fair). It means that the respondents, regardless of their age, neither agree nor disagree on describing the types of 3D Printing they perceived.

Table 2b

Types of 3D Printing Technology perceived by students in terms of age

Age	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
21	3.1667	2	1.17851
22	2.7628	26	0.99462
23	2.1667	3	0.44096
24	3.3333	1	0.0000
Total	2.7500	32	0.95415

Table 2b shows that the entire age of respondents listed above falls on the mean scale of 2.60-3.39 or Fair. It means that the respondents, regardless of their age, neither agree nor disagree on describing the types of 3D Printing they perceived.

Table 2c

Types of 3D Printing Technology perceived by students in terms of geographical location

Geographical Location	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Urban	2.6795	13	1.05071
Rural	2.7982	19	0.90877
Total	2.7500	32	0.95415

Table 2c shows that, regardless of the respondents' living orientation, the mean scale falls in 2.60-3.39 or Fair. It means that the respondents neither agree nor disagree on describing the types of 3D Printing they perceived like in the case in terms of their sex, and age.

Awareness towards 3D Printing among Mechanical Engineering students

Awareness is the one's perception or understanding in something. To identify the perception of mechanical engineering students as a respondents, questions related to awareness have included in the survey. Some of the questions are their familiarity, visualization, accessibility to use, and cost of 3D Printer.

Table 3a

Awareness towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Male	3.1700	20	0.63669
Female	3.2833	12	0.34597
Total	3.2125	32	0.54225

Table 3a above shows that the total population of respondents falls in the mean scale of 2.60-3.39 or Fair. The result revealed that whether they are male or female, they have doubt or neutral understanding on the familiarity and purpose of 3D Printers.

Table 3b

Awareness towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of age

Age	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
21	3.8000	2	0.28284
22	3.2077	26	0.53211
23	2.8000	3	0.60000
24	3.4000	1	0.00000
Total	3.2125	32	0.54225

Table 3b shows that the majority of age groups expressed neutral or fair in their awareness about the 3D Printing technology, whether they agree or disagree. The result falls on the mean scale of 2.60-3.39.

Table 3c

Awareness towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of geographical location

Geographical Location	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Urban	3.1692	13	0.68238
Rural	3.2421	19	0.44010
Total	3.2125	32	0.54225

In the living orientation of respondent, Table 3c shows that whether they live in a city or in province, they expressed their neutral or fair view in their awareness about the 3D Printing technology. The result falls on the mean scale of 2.60-3.39.

In summary, based on the result of the study, the students have low or neutral awareness towards 3D Printing Technology which is similar to the result of the study of Oke, Atofarati, and Bello (2022) which reveals that many individuals have low awareness of 3D printing technology.

Attitude towards 3D Printing among Mechanical Engineering students

Attitude for 3D Printing is a key factor that influence the utilization for industry and in academe. In determining the mechanical engineering students' attitude towards 3D printing, they were asked about the utilization of 3D Printers in the prototype making, knowing more about 3D Printing, and inclusion to the subject curriculum, and training and seminar.

Table 4a

Attitude towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Male	4.1400	20	0.82360
Female	4.2000	12	0.79544
Total	4.1625	32	0.80071

Table 4a reveals that all respondents, either a male or female, have a positive outlook on utilizing the importance and the benefits of 3D Printing. Specifically, females (mean scale falls on 4.20-5.00 - Strongly Agree) show with stronger belief that the the 3D printer is beneficial to the academe and to the curriculum compared to male (falls on 3.40-4.19 - Agree).

Table 4b

Attitude towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of age

Age	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
21	4.4000	2	0.28284
22	4.2385	26	0.79603
23	3.7333	3	0.94516
24	3.0000	1	0.00000
Total	4.1625	32	0.80071

Table 4b shows that the age bracket differs on what are their attitude toward 3D Printing. The younger age have a strong willingness to utilize 3D Printer (mean scale falls on 4.20-5.00 - Strongly Agree), compared to the older ones (falls on 3.40-4.19 - Agree). Overall,

majority of the respondents with regards to their age have a positive response on the importance of 3D Printer in their curriculum and their profession.

Table 4c

Attitude towards 3D Printing perceived by students in terms of geographical location

Geographical Location	Mean	N	Standard Deviation
Urban	4.3077	13	0.73310
Rural	4.0632	19	0.84867
Total	4.1625	32	0.80071

Table 4c shows that the city living respondents have a high level of eagerness to learn and utilize the 3D Printer compared to the province dwellers. Combining the results, respondents, whether in the city or province, have a positive outlook for the 3D printing technology for the inclusion in the subject curriculum.

Based on the result of the study, the students have positive attitude towards 3D Printing Technology which is similar to the result of the study of Maloy, et al. (2017) which reveals in the case of teachers that 3D Printing technology have positive outlook for future lectures.

Determining Significant Differences in the Types of 3D Printing Technology

Table 5a

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Male	2.7500	20	1.07265	0.23985
Female	2.7500	12	0.76045	0.21952

Table 5b

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	0.000	30	1.000
Equal variances not assumed	0.000	29.007	1.000

Using T-test in Table 5b, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 1.0 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of sex.

Table 5c

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of age using ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.713	3	0.571	0.603	0.619
Within Groups	26.510	28	0.947		
Total	28.222	31			

Using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) in Table 5c, the data shows that the significance is 0.619 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of age.

Table 5d

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of graphical location

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Urban	2.6795	13	1.05071	0.29141
Rural	2.7982	19	0.90877	0.20849

Table 5e

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	-0.341	30	0.736
Equal variances not assumed	-0.311	23.350	0.743

Using T-test in Table 5e, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 0.736 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of geographical location.

In summary, the result accepts the null hypothesis in objective which states that there is no significant difference in the types of 3D Printing technology in terms of FDM, Bio-printing, and Construction 3D as perceived among the mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

Determining Significant Differences in the Awareness towards 3D Printing

Table 6a

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Male	3.1700	20	0.63669	0.14237
Female	3.2833	12	0.34597	0.09987

Table 6b

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	-0.566	30	0.576
Equal variances not assumed	-0.652	29.826	0.520

Using T-test in Table 6b, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 0.576 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of sex.

Table 6c

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of age using ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.237	3	0.412	1.465	0.245
Within Groups	7.878	28	0.281		
Total	9.115	31			

Using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) in Table 6c, the data shows that the significance is 0.245 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of age.

Table 6d

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of graphical location

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Urban	3.1692	13	0.68238	0.18926

Rural	3.2421	19	0.44010	0.10096
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Table 6e

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	-0.368	30	0.715
Equal variances not assumed	-0.340	18.788	0.738

Using T-test in Table 6e, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 0.715 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of geographical location.

In summary, the result accepts the null hypothesis in objective stating that there is no significant difference in the awareness towards 3D Printing among mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

Determining Significant Differences in the Attitude towards 3D Printing

Table 7a

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of sex

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Male	4.1400	20	0.82360	0.18416
Female	4.2000	12	0.79544	0.22962

Table 7b

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	-0.202	30	0.841
Equal variances not assumed	-0.204	29.962	0.840

Using T-test in Table 7b, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 0.841 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of sex.

Table 7c

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of age using ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.167	3	0.722	1.142	0.349
Within Groups	17.708	28	0.632		
Total	19.875	31			

Using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) in Table 7c, the data shows that the significance is 0.349 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of age.

Table 7d

Group Statistics of Respondents in terms of graphical location

Sex	Mean	N	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean
Urban	4.3077	13	0.73310	0.20333
Rural	4.0632	19	0.84867	0.19470

Table 7e

Independent Samples Test using T-Test

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Equal variances assumed	0.845	30	0.405
Equal variances not assumed	0.869	28.257	0.392

Using T-test in Table 7e, the data shows that the 2-tailed significance is 0.405 which is greater than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), therefore the result accepts the null hypothesis in terms of geographical location.

In summary, the result accepts the null hypothesis in objective stating that there is no significant difference in the Attitude towards 3D Printing among mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

Determining Significant Relationships of Types of 3D Printing technology, Awareness, and Attitude towards 3D Printing

Table 8

Correlations using Pearson's r method

		Types of 3D Printing Technology	Awareness towards 3D Printing	Attitude towards 3D Printing
Types of 3D Printing Technology	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	0.621	0.429
Awareness towards 3D Printing	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.621	1	0.269
Attitude towards 3D Printing	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.429	0.269	1

Table 8 shows the correlations of three 3 variables with results that the relationship of Awareness towards 3D Printing to Attitude toward 3D Printing with significance of 0.137 and accepts null hypothesis in the objective but the Types of 3D Printing Technology to Awareness and Attitudes towards 3D Printing in their corresponding value of significance is below to the level of significance (0.000 and 0.014 respectively). There are some instances that the students are aware or have perception on what the 3D Printing is, but they do not know all about the Types of 3D Printing technology existing. The same applies in the student's willingness or positive attitude towards 3D Printing but not familiar with the different Types of 3D Printing technology.

DISCUSSION

In relation to the result of this study, the importance of 3D Printing technology gives profound impact to the various sectors and individuals who will benefited from this proposal. Moreover, it gave further increase in awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing among mechanical engineering students in a State University. Several sectors benefited to the findings of the study.

3D printing offers real educational benefits by promoting the culture of active learning, innovation, design, and problem solving. It is holistically tied to STEM education connecting multiple STEM subject areas, particularly the areas of engineering and technology. (Novak, 2022)

In educational institutions, the implications of findings of this study shows that every institution should include the 3D Printing technology to the curriculum so that it could increase the level of awareness and attitude of students towards 3D Printing.

The implications of this findings could include Administrators realizing the increasing knowledge of graduates towards digital fabrications like 3D Printing. If the students posses high level of awareness towards 3D Printing, their graduates will be equipped with extraordinary skills in digital fabrication needed in industry trends. Policymakers in education acknowledged the impact of awareness and attitude of mechanical engineering students towards the importance of 3D Printing technology. They saw the positive effect of the digital fabrication in the field of engineering, and implemented a policy to include 3D Printing technology to the engineering courses for more skills and expertise developed by the graduates. Employers and industry sectors benefited the graduates equipped with skills and expertise in 3D Printing technology. Emerging technology nowadays are evolving to meet the industry trends. These sectors prefer a graduate with high level of awareness and attitude on digital fabrications like 3D Printing to expect competency about digital world workforce.

Faculty and Educators are the mentors of every students in nurturing their capabilities and skills in preparation of career advancement in relation to industry needs. Teachers introducing 3D Printing technology to students gave implications of increasing their level of awareness and attitude leading to innovate creativity and learning experience.

Students are the main beneficiaries of this study. Findings of this research study includes getting higher level of awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing, making students develop interest in digital fabrication, enhancing their practical skills, and fostering creativity and innovation in this digital age.

Lastly, the implication of this findings to researchers is that it increased their awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing and as basis to conduct study in relation to awareness and attitude towards 3D Printing in other institutions.

Conclusions

Through the comprehensive findings of the study, several conclusions were established: In the result of describing the Types of 3D Printing technology, respondents expressed their perception on neutrality or fair with either they agree or disagree regarding on their understanding the different types of 3D Printing. Respondents had confusion on the actual number of different types of 3D Printers available in the market.

In the result of describing the Awareness towards 3D Printing, respondents expressed their perception on neutrality or fair with either they agree or disagree regarding their awareness in 3D Printing whether they have already seen or not, they do not know the actual cost of printer, and they have doubt on popularity of the 3D Printer.

In the result of describing the Attitude towards 3D Printing, respondents expressed their perception on favorable attitude towards the statement but not indicating as strong agreement. Respondents had willingness that the 3D Printers must be utilized, joined in seminars and training, or inclusion in the academia.

In hypothesis number 1, result accepts the null hypothesis in objective which states that there is no significant difference in the types of 3D Printing technology in terms of FDM, Bio-printing, and Construction 3D as perceived among the mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

In hypothesis number 2, result accepts the null hypothesis in objective which states that there is no significant difference in the awareness towards 3D Printing among mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

In hypothesis number 3, result accepts the null hypothesis in objective which states that there is no significant difference in the Attitude towards 3D Printing among mechanical engineering students in a state university taken as an entire group and classified according to sex, age, and geographical location.

In hypothesis number 4, the correlations of three 3 variables with results that the relationship of Awareness towards 3D Printing to Attitude toward 3D Printing with significance of 0.137 and accepts null hypothesis in the objective but the Types of 3D Printing Technology to Awareness and Attitudes towards 3D Printing in their corresponding value of significance is below to the level of significance (0.000 and 0.014 respectively). There are some instances that the students were aware or have perception on what the 3D Printing is but they do not know all about the Types of 3D Printing technology existing. The same thought applies on student's willingness or positive attitude towards 3D Printing but not familiar with the different Types of 3D Printing technology.

Recommendations

In the light of research findings, the recommendation of using 3D Printer in the research prototypes can further explore the potential of student in material selection, design process, and post-processing techniques. Aside from this, using 3D Printing in research prototypes can give the student a choice on customizing design and layout making it unique and with originality.

Due to the evolving technology trends, incorporating hand-on 3D Printing through conducting seminars and training about the 3D Printing can enhance the skills, foster creativity, and engagement of participants to align and cater the needs of industry. 3D Printing training builds collaborations to networking with other trainers, and improve skills development for an industry ready competency.

The academe has a critical role in shaping the student's educational experience. Integration of digital fabrication like 3D Printing to the educational institution enhance the student's skills and expertise in hands-on learning experiences, foster creativity and innovations, and prepare students as a future expert professional in helping diversify the community to meet the technology trends.

Lastly, it is recommended to other aspiring researchers and academicians of diverse program that this research be repeated to confirm the result of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations are implemented in research as it needs to adhere to the code of conduct when it comes to collecting data from participants. The goal of this research is to give information and understanding on the importance of 3D printing for the advancement of technology in the university specifically the fourth year Mechanical Engineering students in integrating the 3D printer in academe. Participants were informed of the risks and they gave consent to answer the survey. Their data were kept with utmost confidentiality. After the survey, the researcher collected the answered questionnaire.

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REFERENCES

- 3DPrinting.com. (2024, January 6). What is 3D printing? How does a 3D printer work? Learn 3D printing. 3D Printing. <https://3dprinting.com/what-is-3d-printing/>
- Banks, S. (2023, March 29). 3D printing research at Stanford. Stanford Report. <https://news.stanford.edu/stories/2023/03/3d-printing-research-stanford>
- CIIT Philippines School - Multimedia Arts, Web Design, 3D Animation, Mobile Game Development. (2019, December 16). CIIT adapts 3D technology through the use of 3D printers. <https://www.ciit.edu.ph/news-feed/ciit-3d-printers/>
- Connectivism learning Theory. (2024, March 19). Western Governors University. <https://www.wgu.edu/blog/connectivism-learning-theory2105.html>
- EvalCommunity. (2023, October 31). Utilizing SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). [https://www.evalcommunity.com/career-center/using-spss-in-monitoring-and-evaluation/#:~:text=Social%20Sciences\)%3F-,SPSS%20\(Statistical%20Package%20for%20the%20Social%20Sciences\)%20is%20a%20software,data%20management%2C%20and%20data%20visualization.](https://www.evalcommunity.com/career-center/using-spss-in-monitoring-and-evaluation/#:~:text=Social%20Sciences)%3F-,SPSS%20(Statistical%20Package%20for%20the%20Social%20Sciences)%20is%20a%20software,data%20management%2C%20and%20data%20visualization.)
- Oke, A.E., Atofarati, J.O., and Bello, S.F., (2022, June). Awareness of 3D Printing for Sustainable Construction in an Emerging Economy. <https://search.informit.org/doi/epdf/10.3316/informit.715146401831631>
- Ishutov, S., Hodder, K., Chalaturnyk, R., & Zambrano-Narvaez, G. (2021). A 3D printing Short Course: A Case Study for Applications in the Geoscience Teaching and Communication for Specialists and Non-experts. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.601530>
- Frost, J. (2024). Content Validity: Definition, Examples & Measuring. *Statistics by Jim*. <https://statisticsbyjim.com/basics/content-validity/>
- Houston, K. (2024, February 8). 5 types of questionnaires. www.jotform.com. <https://www.jotform.com/blog/types-of-questionnaire/>
- Kwon, Y. M., Lee, Y., & Kim, S. J. (2017). Case study on 3D printing education in fashion design coursework. *Fashion and Textiles*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-017-0111-3>
- Novak, E. (2022, May 30). 3D printing in education. www.taylorfrancis.com. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/entries/10.4324/9781138609877-REE81-1/3d-printing-education-elena-novak?context=rroe>
- Wohlin, C., Höst, M., Runeson, P., & Wesslén, A. (2003). Software reliability. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 25–39). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b0-12-227410-5/00858-9>